

Legal Challenges for the Law of the Sea and Maritime Law in the Light of Disruptive Technologies – Modular and Autonomous Submarines

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Abstract— The present paper concerns the legal evaluation of technological progress. It assumes that disruptive technologies change the circumstances in which an international treaty was drafted leading to an incompatibility of the current legal framework with such innovative products. To illustrate this phenomenon, the article introduces the project of the company ThyssenKrupp Marine Systems, the Modifiable Underwater Mothership (MUM). Using an autonomous and modular design, this product seems to not fit into the existing law of the sea.

Keywords—international maritime law, law of the sea, autonomous navigation, modularity, submarines, disruptive technologies

I. INTRODUCTION

The legal regulation of technology is a challenge that grows with the dynamics of technological development. The law has a wide variety of functions, such as ensuring and promoting technical development, but also limiting it with regard to potential dangers [1]. As a rule, the law lags behind technical development [2], without this necessarily resulting in damage or delays in development. Existing law can also be applied to new technological possibilities without being updated, provided it is designed in the abstract and a contemporary interpretation is applied. Moreover, law can be prepared for future developments to a limited extent by anticipating them in the genesis of the law.

A particular challenge with regard to the relationship between law and technologic innovations is posed by so-called disruptive technologies. In the legal sense, technologies are disruptive if they create new facts and challenge the existing reality which the lawmakers could not have anticipated in their time. Due to their innovation potential, these technologies displace the existing ones from the market in a very short time. New application possibilities of disruptive technologies give rise to both products and services that were previously not feasible, and in some cases not even foreseeable. This is the point where conflicts with existing law can arise. In such a case, existing law usually assumes an outdated technological reality that does not take these new possibilities into account. Although new products and services can be regulated by interpreting the existing legal framework, this often leads to restrictions on the new technologies that were not intended by the original legislator. The existing law was designed for a past everyday reality in

which now outdated technologies shaped the prevailing products and services as well as their usage and employment. Since disruptive technologies usually also change the landscape of risks and potentials to be regulated, existing law must be adapted to a new reality.

To show said interaction between law and technological development regarding a specific application, this article is based on a project led by German shipbuilding company ThyssenKrupp Marine Systems called *Modifiable Underwater Mothership* (MUM) [3]. The ship encapsulates different innovations that one might qualify as disruptive. Firstly, MUM will operate unmanned and autonomously. Furthermore, the ship has a modular design and an electric propulsion. Indeed, such novel technologies are not easily covered by today's applicable legal framework. Moreover, MUM will be able to operate both on and below the sea surface [4] which is a feature not yet utilized in traditional commercial navigation. This article takes these three different elements of MUM as an example to show the incompatibility of the current public international law of the sea framework with those innovations.

II. UNMANNED AND AUTONOMOUS NAVIGATION

The first issue of this paper concerns the usage of autonomous and unmanned ships in international law. The benefits and advantages of this technology have been widely discussed and include *inter alia* the elimination of human errors due to fatigue and lack of concentration [5], cost reduction due to savings in crewing and fuel consumption [6] as well as environmental benefits [7]. Although this topic has seen considerably more attention in the international community as well as the literature than the other topics of this article, the underlying legal problems are far from solved. This section attempts to give an overview of the problems that still hinder the emergence of autonomous and unmanned ships and shows transitory practices and possibilities until said legal barriers are resolved.

Beginning with the terminology, the definitions and terms that are discussed seem to vary. The commonly used expression Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships (MASS) was developed by the Maritime Safety Committee (MSC) of the International Maritime Organization (IMO). However, the umbrella organization Maritime UK uses the term Maritime Autonomous Ships System in its Code of Practice,

thereby including underwater vehicles as well [8]. Other scholars use the rather neutral expression maritime autonomous vehicles (MAV) [9] or unmanned marine vehicles (UMV) [10]. Concerning the subject matter of autonomous ships, IMO defines four degrees of autonomy. These include (1) ships with automated processes and crew on board, (2) remotely controlled ships with crew on board, (3) remotely controlled ships without seafarers on board and (4) fully autonomous ships [11]. Yet, as was pointed out by RINGBOM, these four rather rigid categories cannot display the full range of uses for MASS [12]. On the one hand, the manning level is not directly related to the level of autonomy since a fully autonomous ship can also be crewed or only periodically manned. [13] On the other hand, there is a wider range of autonomy than the categories ‘no autonomy’ and ‘fully autonomous’ (e.g. monitored, constrained or temporary autonomy) [14]. Thus, a more distinguished and stringent terminology is necessary to fully illustrate the whole variety of unmanned and autonomous navigation. Eventually, the exact degree of autonomy and the level of manning will be decided by the shipbuilders with the consequence that the legal framework should try to anticipate all aspects that will occur in the development of MASS. With regard to regulatory barriers, it is especially important to distinguish the autonomy level from the manning level when discussing MASS. That is because most of the regulatory issues stem from the manning element rather than from the autonomous nature of a maritime vehicle. However, autonomous navigation – in the sense of decision making without human influence – may give rise to cybersecurity and liability issues or even ethical questions [15].

To assess the focal elements that need to be regulated in order to secure safe navigation of autonomous and unmanned vessels, the MSC has conducted a Regulatory Scoping Exercise (RSE) that was concluded in June 2021 [16]. In this study, the member States examined the relevant IMO instruments and worked out the common gaps and topics that need to be either amended in the existing instruments or addressed in a new instrument concerning autonomous vehicles. The RSE concluded that the topics master, crew, responsible persons, remote operation center and remote operators belong to the highest priority issues [17], which was essentially also identified by various authors in the literature [18]. In addition to that, the MSC gave recommendations on how to appropriately address the relevant instruments, i.e. whether no further action needs to be undertaken, an existing instrument could be amended or a new instrument should be drafted (or none of the above). Among the commonly addressed instruments that pose legal barriers to autonomous and unmanned ships – both in the RSE and in other literature – are the Safety of Life at Sea Convention (SOLAS [19]), the International Regulations for Preventing Collisions at Sea (COLREG [20]) and the International Convention on Standards of Training, Certification and Watchkeeping for Seafarers (STCW [21]). All three instruments serve the purpose of protection of human lives at sea and thus, they presuppose the presence of human beings on board of the ship [22]. One example from SOLAS is that ‘in areas of high traffic density, in conditions of restricted visibility and in all other hazardous navigational situations where heading and/or track control systems are in use, it shall be possible to

establish manual control of the ship’s steering immediately’. [23] To comply with such a rule one might try to look for technical solutions, for example a remotely controlled ship in the mentioned spaces. But creating an equal standard of safety and security as traditional navigation by remotely controlling a ship might be hindered by technical barriers. Other regulations entirely lack a scope of application for unmanned ships as their object and purpose is actually based on the condition of people present on board; this is exemplified by SOLAS Chapter II-2 Regulation 10 section 3 requiring a certain amount of portable fire extinguishers on ships for firefighting. These examples show that introducing unmanned ships into the current system ‘requires a complete rethinking of the centuries of maritime standards, traditions and customs’ [24].

However, before tackling the issue of implementing MASS into the current shipping framework – i.e. by adapting the present rules or creating a novel instrument – the preliminary question, whether the IMO is actually the logical starting point for regulating autonomous and unmanned ships, needs to be answered [25]. For that purpose, one must take a closer look at the relationship and interdependency between the Law of the Sea Convention (LOSC [26]), the IMO and MASS; as constitution of the ocean, the LOSC is of utmost importance for the regulation of MASS. The codification of the law of the sea started with the Hague Conference for the Codification of International Law as early as 1930 with the predominant aim to codify existing law of the sea [27]. This shows that many principles guiding the law of the sea are almost a century old. The final draft of the LOSC was adopted in 1982 which entered into force in 1994. When creating LOSC 40 to 60 years ago, lawmakers were bound by the reality of traditional navigation at the time, not considering any potentially unmanned or autonomous ships [28]. Thus, the rules of the LOSC – while not explicitly requiring permanent manning – expect the ship to be manned and to be navigated by a crew [29]. Important examples are the duty of flag States to exercise effective jurisdiction over the master and the crew, Art. 94(4)(b) LOSC, and, depending on the precise obligation under this norm, the duty to render assistance for people in danger at sea, Art. 98 LOSC. These norms clearly draw the picture of vessels that are manned and navigated by human beings. Further research will be necessary to conclusively determine whether these rules preclude unmanned and autonomous navigation from the LOSC in its entirety – and therefore need to be changed – or whether the LOSC can be interpreted in an evolutionary manner to fit MASS into its regime. Bearing this in mind, it is further important to note the interdependencies between the LOSC and IMO instruments. In multiple instances, via so-called renvoi clauses, the LOSC refers to general accepted international rules and standards that are set by the IMO. This leads to the special constellation that ‘instruments that were developed under the auspices of IMO (...) operate within the framework of the LOSC’ [30]. If the IMO regulates an issue that contradicts fundamental principles of the LOSC, this regulatory mechanism then becomes void. As a result, it must be ensured ‘that the elaboration of IMO instruments conformed with the basic principles guiding the elaboration of the LOSC’ [31]. However, as the LOSC is not a convention drafted under the auspices of IMO, none of its committees

considered the application of the LOSC to MASS. The MASS working group of the IMO merely considered that MASS must comply with the legal framework of the LOSC and therefore, the LOSC needs to be considered in IMO's future work on MASS. [32] There was, however, no regulatory scoping exercise that examines potential legal barriers that stem from the LOSC.

Until a complete framework for MASS has been concluded, there is a legal lacuna on how autonomous and unmanned navigation shall be conducted so as not to violate international law of the sea and international maritime law. For this transition period, the MSC has published a set of interim guidelines for MASS trials. Those guidelines are centered around a single rule. They oblige stakeholders (e.g. coastal State, flag State, port State and other entities involved in MASS trials) to conduct trials 'in a manner that provides at least the same degree of safety, security and protection of the environment as provided by the relevant instrument' [33]. By that, the MSC turns the object and purpose of the relevant instruments into an abstract obligation to fulfil due diligence (so-called goal-based standard). That means that the rule only outlines the objectives to be achieved. The detailed means of achieving those objectives are left to flag States, classification societies, and ship designers and builders. Therefore, if a new technology can comply with the overall goals set out in the ruleset, it can be implemented into the legal framework. This goal-based approach is also the regulatory technique to regulate MASS as a whole [34]. The interim guidelines, however, are in two ways problematic: First, their application is – by definition [35] – limited to the period of time needed for the trial and thus not applicable beyond the trial phase of MASS. Secondly, the substantial rule to be followed is rather broad and leaves much need for clarification because it is unclear what safety standards of conventional navigation are to be followed *mutatis mutandis*. More technical details are provided by the different classification societies that developed guidelines for the development of autonomous ships [36]. Nonetheless, these guidelines are not a legally binding ruleset and merely reflect possible interpretations of international regulations which might lead to conflict if future instruments are based on different interpretations thereof. Yet, for the time being, shipowners, shipbuilders and operators are well-advised to communicate their propositions to classification societies since they provide a certain standard of safety in construction and conduct – rather than no standard at all. In addition to that, the design, construction and maintenance of ships shall be in accordance with the structural, mechanical and electrical requirements of such a recognized classification society under SOLAS II-1 [37].

As for now, the IMO has decided on its 104th session to include the development of a goal-based instrument for MASS in its biennial agenda for 2022-2023 with a completion targeted for 2025. While this approach does not solve the issue concerning the relationship between the LOSC and IMO on the development of MASS rules, it does offer a practicable ruleset for the ship industry to comply with. Such a ruleset would be more detailed than the interim guidelines for MASS trials and – if developed as an independent treaty that states could become a member of – more binding than

the technically detailed rules and guidelines of the classification societies. In any case, such a ruleset would help to solve at least some of the legal uncertainties with the (hopefully) beneficial effect that more and more stakeholders actually start projects on autonomous and unmanned ships in the international playing field.

III. MODULAR SHIP DESIGN

Another key property of the MUM project is the concept of modularity. MUM is developed around the idea that its constituting parts are standardized and can be adapted depending on the mission to be carried out. Those components are also called modules and not only are they parts of the ship but they constitute the structure of the ship. Thus, depending on the number and nature of modules, such properties as the functionality and technical features of the ship will change during the operational life of the ship [38]. This is what ERIKSTAD designates as 'operational modularity' [39].

Modularity as such is not a new feature within the scope of ship building. The geopolitical context explains why several States across the world have decided to turn towards this technical innovation in order to face new post- Cold War threats that required 'mobility and swiftness' [40]. For instance, the United States' Navy developed the Littoral Combat Ship (LCS) defined as follows: 'the LCS is less of a ship, and more of a battle network component system, consisting of a sea frame, a core crew, assorted mission modules, assembled mission packages, mission package crews, and a reconfiguration support structure' [41]. This definition shows that a ship's modularity implies the assembly of several self-sufficient modules that could work in different settings. However, it should be stressed that MUM is set out to be a civilian ship, contrarily to many existing modular ships. Moreover, the hull structure of the LCS is not impacted by the possibility to swap modules, contrarily to MUM. Thus, the extent to which the ship at hand applies modular concepts reaches well beyond already existing examples and justifies its disruptive character.

ERIKSTAD in his work on ship modularity sees two points in carrying out operational modularity as applied to ships. First, the ability to execute swifter repairs in the case of a failing component and second, the capacity to adapt to new regulations and/or missions [42]. Because MUM is constituted by interchangeable standardised modules, it can also fulfil both these objectives. However, from a legal standpoint these two aspects may present some incompatibilities with the law of the sea as it currently exists. These incompatibilities are threefold. First, directly linked to the possibility to carry out swifter repairs is the question of which stakeholder carries the responsibility to ensure maintenance of the various instruments onboard. Because the components of a modular ship can be standardised, the original equipment manufacturer who conceived these modules may be more suited to carry out maintenance activities. The classification society DNV also advocates this idea [43]. Traditionally, it is the end user of the vessel who executes such duties, as it is to be understood from the International Safety Management Code (ISM [44]) [45]. However, this same provision does not appear to leave room

for other stakeholders to be responsible for maintenance. Thus, shifting the responsibility in this area stumbles on a first hurdle. Second, switching modules in order to fulfil a new mission may involve a change in the functionality of the ship. It can be well imaginable that a module made to carry out civilian activities such as marine scientific research (MSR) could be replaced with military modules. This would blur the distinction between civilian objects and military objects as set out by customary international humanitarian law [46]. Moreover, looking at LOSC Art. 29 to 32, different rules apply to military vessels. Third, as explained before, some ships like the LCS may see their sea frame built around the possibility to welcome different modules serving different purposes. In the case of the MUM project, because the modules are constituting the sea frame, their rearrangement involves the modification of the ship's properties such as the length, the stability, etc. Those properties offered by the MUM project could be seen as standing in opposition with international provisions such as the ones issued by the IMO. SOLAS refers on several occasion to the length of the ship that is supposed to be a fixed feature. For instance, the calculation of the floodable length according to the annex of SOLAS, Chapter II-1, Part B, Regulation 3 is entirely dependent of the overall length of the ship. SOLAS makes countless other references to the length of the ship when it comes to fire protection, openings or compartments among others. The convention does not per se establish that the length of the ship cannot be changed, but it was drafted at a time when considering ships with varying length was out of question. Thus, it appears that an ever-changing length would only be difficult to conciliate with IMO conventions, in particular SOLAS.

However, the biggest difficulty might lie within the role played by classification societies. According to SOLAS, Chapter I, Part B, Regulation 6, the inspection and survey of ships may be entrusted to 'surveyors nominated for the purpose or to organizations recognized by it'. The organisations in question are classification societies which ensure that technical requirements are fulfilled by the ship owners. One of their most important mission is to assign a class to the ships but also to carry out surveys and inspection onboard. Depending on the class, different regulations have to be followed. [47] Thus, if the properties upon which the ship was classified change we could face a discrepancy between the observations made during inspection of the ship and its actual constitution. A classification society such as DNV addresses this issue in its guideline on conversion of ships. [48] Among the elements that can lead to such a conversion, the lengthening of a vessel is to find. [49] Thus, it appears that a ship – if it were to be classified by DNV – would have to involve the classification society every time that its length changes. For a normal ship, whose technical properties do not rely on such a feature, this may not be an issue. However, for a project such as MUM, which made one of its core innovations to be modularity, it would represent a grave impediment to the commercialisation of the ship.

IV. LEGAL ISSUES OF CIVIL SUBMARINES

Autonomous systems, as well as innovative electric propulsion systems, are enabling the construction of new types of submarines that do not require crews or the pressure-

sensitive cabins that they require. The MUM ship, for example, is a water-flooded submarine that eliminates pressure-sensitive cavities. This design removes two major hurdles that made, on the one hand, submarines dangerous to operate, and on the other hand technically and financially costly. [50] Accordingly, submarines were previously used only in MSR and military applications. [51]

New technologies now make it possible to build submarines of a size (up to 100 m in length and even more) and with capabilities (e.g. diving depth of 5000 m) that were previously prohibitively expensive for civilian applications. [52] The extent to which improved access to the underwater world will be exploited by the maritime industry is yet to be seen. Obvious applications for vessels such as MUM are most likely in the area of seafloor exploration. Nonetheless, the possibility of new players using submarines in the submarine environment should be sufficient to evaluate the submarine regulatory regime.

A look at international maritime law quickly reveals that submarines are not explicitly or separately regulated. Only in international humanitarian law, the 1936 London Protocol on the Rules of Submarine Warfare, there is an international agreement that explicitly regulates the use of submarines. Even Article 20 LOSC, the only explicit rule mentioning submarines in the Law of the Sea Convention, is authoritatively designed for military vessels. [53] It requires submarines to navigate on the surface in territorial waters while showing their flag. Although the wording of this rule also applies to civilian submarines, there were no civilian examples of its application at the time it was drafted.

This fact that there are to date no significant civilian applications of large submarines is also mainly responsible for the lack of independent agreements on the civil use of submarines. Much of the existing maritime law is 50 years old or older. The underlying negotiations and drafts are often additional decades older, so that current maritime law roughly represents the technical state of the post-World War II era. Accordingly, the creators of the current law did not have civilian submarines in mind when they drafted the maritime and navigation law agreements. Rather, predominantly warships, as well as ships smaller than a specified size (e.g. smaller than 24 m in length or a gross tonnage less than 500) were excluded from application of the international conventions. In the past, this has meant that small submarines for scientific purposes have generally not been affected by international maritime law. Based on this premise, two consequences follow:

A. There is a lack of regulations for the large-scale deployment of civilian submarines

The most concise example for this is the restriction of COLREG to surface navigation. [54] The focus on surface navigation already follows from the definition of the term 'vessel' in Rule 3 COLREG, which is based on its use as a means of transport on water. In addition, the collision avoidance rules often presuppose visual contact between vessels or the existence of radar information. They are therefore unsuitable for underwater navigation and only affect submarines while they are surfaced. Collision avoidance rules for underwater navigation would have to take into account, on the one hand, the limited perceptive capability and, on the other hand, the three-dimensionality of navigation.

The limitation of IMO regulations to surface navigation seems to gain new relevance due to the incompatibility of the current law with autonomous or unmanned navigation. Thus, the IMO's reform efforts focus on MASS. [55] However, the IMO must not fall prey to overlooking the fact that the possibility of unmanned navigation makes it possible to open up the underwater world.

B. The current law is applicable, but not compatible with civilian submarines

It is already questionable whether submarines are covered by the ship definition of some IMO conventions. [56] The aforementioned definition from COLREG casts doubt on its applicability to submarines. However, also in COLREG Rule 3, underwater operations are cited as a regulatory example of 'ships limited in manoeuvrability', implying applicability to submarines. In contrast to COLREG, the term 'ship' is not even defined in many IMO conventions, and the term 'submarine' is not mentioned. An exception is the MARPOL Convention [57], which explicitly defines submersibles as ships in Article 2. If one finally adds Art. 20 LOSC, which lays down rules for submarines in 'Subsection A. Rules applicable to all ships', then at least the tendency becomes clear that in international maritime law submarines are understood as ships.

The International Convention on Load Lines exemplifies that the application of IMO conventions to submarines may not have been intended or considered by their creators. [58] The purpose of the 1966 Load Line Convention is to prevent the overloading of seagoing vessels and thus to prevent serious accidents involving cargo ships. [59] By setting a maximum draught for ships, its aim is to ensure their seaworthiness. This limit is marked by affixing a freeboard mark to the hull of the ships. Setting a maximum draught for submarines does not make sense, as submerged travel is the design purpose of a submarine. Nevertheless, submarines are not exempted from the application of the Load Line Convention. It can be assumed that the exemptions for warships and ships smaller than 24 m in length according to Article 5 of the Load Lines Convention were considered sufficient in the 1960s to *de facto* exclude submarines as well. Large civilian submarines, however, are contrary to the wording of the Convention and would consequently have to be given a freeboard mark. In response to this legal absurdity, the US Coast Guards ignore the lack of a freeboard mark on submarines in accordance with the USCG Load Line Policy Notes, contrary to the international obligation that nevertheless exists. [60]

Comparable incompatibilities arise in the application of SOLAS. The exceptions of the Convention according to Chapter I Regulation 3 are also limited to warships and ships of less than 500 gross tonnage, with the consequence that large civilian submarines are subject to the Convention. Two obligations under SOLAS exemplify its incompatibility with submarines:

- SOLAS chapter VI regulation 12 requires every ship to continuously monitor specified radio frequencies. In underwater navigation, the reception of radio signals is regularly not possible.
- SOLAS chapter V regulation 22 contains requirements for the field of vision on the navigation bridge which seem nonsensical for a submarine in submerged navigation. For example, a view of the sea surface should be guaranteed from the bridge.

These obligations give rise to the suspicion that the SOLAS regulations were written primarily with surface ships in mind. [61]

As an interim result, it should be noted that international maritime law is not designed for submarines but primarily for surface vessels. Consequently, there is a lack of rules that address the challenges posed by underwater navigation. Furthermore, the existing law contains obligations that are not applicable to or compatible with submarines. Should the civilian use of submarines increase due to new technological possibilities, maritime law would be confronted with numerous needs for change.

V. CONCLUSION

The previous examples show that innovative technologies which create a new reality may not fit into the legal system. To a specific point, interpretation of existing rules is not sufficient to make legal compliance possible. To cope with this problem there are two possible ways to go forward. The first possibility is to adapt technological innovation to the legal framework within the rules of legal interpretation. This is the easiest and most reliable way for scientists to ensure legal compliance. However, this might be excluding innovation and hinder technologic progress. The second option is to adapt the legal framework in the light of innovative and disruptive technologies. Changing the law should then strive to enable technologic innovation as far as possible. How this could be possible is exemplified by the procedure around autonomous navigation: The IMO plans to adopt a new body of law to holistically regulate autonomous navigation by using the Goal Based Standards. Therefore, if a new technology can comply with the overall goals set out in the ruleset, it can be implemented into the legal framework.

To conclude this paper, one should bear the following question in mind: What good is innovative technology and progressive design if those technologies and designs are not lawful and can thus not be used? This problem, however, shows two sides of the same coin: Not only should technologies be developed with the legal framework in mind. In addition to that, the legal framework must also be flexible enough or at least be sufficiently changeable to allow innovation of technology. A cooperation of natural and legal sciences is especially important to avoid a vicious cycle: The development of a new legal framework relies on the specifics and details of the emerging technologies that ought to be regulated. On the other hand, the developments of new technologies can be barred from fully evolving due to a lack of legal certainty. To break out from this cycle, it is of the utmost importance that both sides – the scientific and legal research – acknowledge the interdependency between each other and thoroughly cooperate in the process of innovation.

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